

Interview Transcript

Peter Boot, Elena Chestnova

November 13, 2025, 1:00PM (CET)

Introduction

The following interview was conducted in the context of the research project “ReSED API - Re-Use Standards for Editions Data with Application Programming Interfaces” funded by Swissuniversities in the period 01.07.2025 – 30.12.2026. Overall, ten interviews were conducted with the aim of consulting scholars who have detailed knowledge of the digital humanities and editions landscape to find out which data sharing and re-use practices they currently observe, and where the potential for broadening and deepening them lies.

The interviewee, in this case Dr. Peter Boot from the Huygens Institute of the Royal Netherlands Academy of Arts and Sciences, was sent a basic info questionnaire and a list of questions in preparation for a semi-structured interview which took place over video-chat. The transcript was generated by the integrated tool of MS Teams and edited by both participants of the interview. The publication of the transcript follows explicit consent given by the interviewee.

Chestnova Elena 0:05

CE

As I mentioned in my e-mail, the idea of these interviews is to “take the temperature” of the digital humanities and digital editing community around data reuse and APIs.

To start with, could you please give a little bit of context in terms of your institutional context and in terms of your background and research specialisms?

Peter Boot 0:31

PB

Yes, I can. So, I'm working at the Huygens Institute which is an institute belonging to the Royal Netherlands Academy of Arts and Sciences. Huygens Institute works on, let's say, the whole written history of the Netherlands from the medieval period until the present day. What we do is publication of very many different types of historical sources. They may be medieval manuscripts, they may be letters, they may be diaries. Also, it depends on the source that you publish. Sometimes these publications are really scholarly digital editions, where every word has been the subject of careful thought. There are also mass publications of historical documents. For instance, we published all the resolutions of the Dutch Parliament for two centuries until 1800, and that's too much material to do anything else than OCR and some entity recognition. So, the whole scale of publishing from mass publication up to very detailed publication.

My own background is... I work both in software development and I have a degree in Dutch literary studies, so my own position in projects is often as a linking pin between the developers and the humanities researchers who create the editions. The editions that I've been working on are mostly in the literary field and also echo documents such as diaries and letters, etc.

Chestnova Elena 2:36

CE

Great. Thank you. I saw on the form that you sent me, you've both reused the data that was

created by others and that some of your data has been reused. Could you tell me a little bit about that, what kinds of data those were, in what context and so on?

Peter Boot 2:55

PB

In the preparation of this interview, I've been thinking about all of the things that we've been building over the last 20-25 years. And of course I've not been involved with all of the individual projects, but for instance one project that I started out with when working in the field of digital editions was an edition of Dutch Emblem Books. Emblems... I don't know whether you know the emblem, but it's a genre of pictures and mostly poems from the 16th and 17th century. This was a popular genre in many different European countries, and there were many different projects in European countries who were working on their national emblem tradition. And so we worked together and created an exchange mechanism using the OAI PMH protocol in order to be able to create collections which contained all of the emblem descriptions from the various projects.

So that's one example. Another example is we created an edition of the letters of Vincent Van Gogh, already 15 years ago. It took some convincing to make the management agree to publication of the XML of those letters, but quickly after we published the XML, this was used by the people at TEI Publisher. They created their own version of the letters based on our XML to showcase what you can do with TEI Publisher.

Another reuse case which I see, but that's a sort of internal reuse. We created this Van Gogh Edition, but now we are beginning to see that the digital infrastructure of that edition is getting very old. It was built in a programming language no longer well supported, so we are now reusing the material from that edition in order to create a new version of that edition. We also reuse some material from other sites. There's in the Netherlands an institution which is now at the National Library, the Digital Library of Dutch Literature (DBNL), and it creates, let's say, very simple elementary editions of printed works from the past. So they have a simple TEI scheme, which all of their editions conform to, and for quite a lot of our editions we have started with the XML that they created in order to enhance it and enrich it. So, for instance, we have a collection of letters from the 17th century of various learned persons to each other (Republic of Letters), and most of these letters come from this elementary digital library, and so we created a collection based on that. There are a number of projects which have used this type of reuse.

Chestnova Elena 6:53

CE

Do you think that the reuse scenarios in which you've been involved are typical for the editions community and the digital humanities community? And are there many people who are doing something like that? Or would you say that it's not widespread?

Peter Boot 7:13

PB

I would think that this is... I would think it's not uncommon. Well, maybe the use of the OAI PMH protocol, I don't see that often. It's also very old of course. The reuse of existing XML, that's a really easy form of reuse, of course. It doesn't require you to build something like an API or something like that. You can just start from existing XML and work with that and do your own thing with it. So in a sense, it's a low level reuse mostly, I think.

CE **Chestnova Elena** 8:09

And is your feeling around the community or your colleagues, you also mentioned discussions with the management, do you think there is a good balanced understanding of reuse, what you can achieve with reuse, and why you might want to make your data open for reuse or do you think there are certain barriers to that?

PB **Peter Boot** 8:33

Well, things have also changed. I think that the management position at our institute and at the Netherlands Academy in general is that we should work as much as possible open source and Open Access. So, at the moment the Institute fully accepts that as much as possible, if there are no copyright restrictions or otherwise, we should publish everything that we do and make it accessible for other researchers. For instance, we use Pure to measure our research production and there's also fields to register the data sets that you produced and it's encouraged to do so.

CE **Chestnova Elena** 9:30

Do you think that this is a specifically Dutch thing, or have you heard of other countries that also have structures to encourage this type of thing? Because in Switzerland we don't really have it. I mean it's recommended, but nobody really checks, and so you don't really get anything proactively extra for publishing your data openly. People do it because they believe in the idea of open data.

PB **Peter Boot** 9:57

I wouldn't know about other countries. My feeling is that the world of scholarship is certainly in general moving towards Open Access and open publication forms. Also, the funders in the Netherlands, the scholarly scientific funders, require you to do Open Access and open data as much as possible.

CE **Chestnova Elena** 10:31

Do you think this is connected with the fact that in the Netherlands there is an advanced research data infrastructure? We invited colleagues from the Netherlands here to talk about how the infrastructures work in the Netherlands because it's really quite an excellent example.

PB **Peter Boot** 10:56

Yeah, I must say, I don't know enough about how this is set up in other countries. It might well be related to it. Yes, I suppose so.

CE **Chestnova Elena** 11:09

Great. Thank you. You've also mentioned that you've both used and set up APIs for digital humanities resources. Could you talk briefly about that?

Peter Boot 11:24

PB

Set up an API...

One of the things that I wanted to mention, this is not so much something that I do myself, but I know our development group, or at least a part of the group that we work most with, which is responsible for the publication of textual resources, has designed a publication system where everything that we create as sources is converted into the format of web annotations, an interrelated bunch of web annotations. So we create TEI XML, but then this is entirely stripped, let's say in the form of one stream of text and a lot of annotations on this text. And all of these annotations together embody the complete TEI, sometimes there's even some extra analysis already in these annotations and these annotations are all available online. I don't think they advertise that as yet but let's say every detail of the data is in principle individually addressable and accessible from the outside world.

Yeah, well, it's not exactly an API, but the data can be queried from outside.

I've tried to convince the development group also to look at Distributed Text Services, I would very much love our editions to be accessible using DTS. But because they already have this other feature, and because development hours are always scarce, at the moment we have not been able to build that into our publications.

Another thing which has never led to any real usage, but in my thesis I designed an API for annotations on editions. The idea was that you would be able to use an annotation tool on a digital edition and the annotation tool would store the annotation and would function as sort of server which you could query using something very much like the OAI PMH. And of course you would use web annotations for that purpose now. But the idea is that you should have an API in order to make your resources accessible from the outside world, I think you really would want that. On the other hand, I'm also beginning to think that... I wrote an article once together with Joris van Zundert about how we shouldn't think in terms of resources, but in terms of services. And so, a digital edition would be a resource, yes, but it would also perhaps consist of a set of services which were collecting information from various resources and in that vision, of course, APIs are essential. On the other hand, it also supposes that all these APIs remain available and that all the services remain working and I think we see all too often that services are discontinued. So, it makes you much more vulnerable.

This was mostly about the APIs that we provide. You also asked about having used APIs.

We use IIF all the time. In experimental publications, I've been using the API of TEI publisher. I think there are probably more, but those are the ones that I could think of.

Chestnova Elena 17:07

CE

On the subject of long-term usability, something that's come up during these interviews often is the trend that we certainly have in Switzerland, and I think in some other countries as well, towards making editions static. So basically, pre-coding everything in HTML and just having static pages. Do you have this in the Netherlands and what impact do you think this might make on data sharing, reusability and on the argument for APIs?

Peter Boot 17:29

PB

I think it's not a thing that many people are concerned with. I know that some of the older

editions that we have are really based on a database in a very old system, and that if the database would stop running, the edition is gone. There's much to say for simple static resources. But at the moment, really, everything that we publish requires a server. And yes, yes, it would be very nice, but it's hard enough to get it working with the server.

Chestnova Elena 18:57

CE

Thank you. In your experience of using APIs, what do you think makes a successful API? Is the success of an API within the technology of the API, within the structure? Or is the success actually in the data that comes into it? The way it has been documented and structured, and so on.

Peter Boot 19:23

PB

Yeah, that's hard to say. I think it's a combination of those things. So why has IIF become such success? Well because of its wide adoption. Many institutions understanding that it's really madness to each have your own way of providing images. And, of course, because the images are very important and attractive to include in your publications and the publicity of the API is also another factor. The availability of tools. I wouldn't know which one is more important, but I think those four, I think, I mentioned would be relevant in these respects.

Chestnova Elena 20:22

CE

And do you find that when you speak to colleagues... within your specialist field, they probably understand what an API is and why you might want one, but when you speak to colleagues that are a bit more on the traditional humanities side, is it easy to communicate to them what an API is and why they might want to have one?

Peter Boot 20:45

PB

No, that's not easy.

For something like IIF they understand that. For more traditional humanities people, that's just a part of the technology. OK, you use the API. Why not? But that it might also be useful to have an API into the resources that we are creating from their data, I think that's mostly not an idea that they're familiar with, or that it's easy to explain.

Reuse, yes. So, we published the edition of Van Gogh's letters, and a few months later there was an Italian journal a designer who had taken the trouble of creating wonderful visualisations on the basis of the words occurring in the XML, and that's something that everybody understands. But an API is something much more abstract and I also think that [there are] not that many examples of sites which actually function on the basis of an API fetching data from another site.

Chestnova Elena 22:33

CE

Do you think the humanities landscape or the "humanities internet", so to speak, would benefit from a wider adoption of APIs?

Peter Boot 22:40

PB

Yes, in principle, yes. But with the reservation of the sustainability, for instance, now that we are seeing in the US all sorts of resources being taken offline or cleansed of things that Trump thinks inappropriate? Well, that's one reason to think, well, maybe it's better to copy some data than to have a service that fetches the data from elsewhere and then having someone who doesn't like that data remove it and yeah, there are two sides to it.

Chestnova Elena 23:38

CE

What would be the positive aspect of API adoption from your point of view?

Peter Boot 23:45

PB

Well, the positive aspects would be that you could create resources that are really helping the researcher contextualise the material that he or she is researching. I once wrote an article about when I was still working on Emblem studies about how a virtual research environment for an emblem researcher would look like. What you would have, for instance, is APIs which go into historical dictionaries and into these various emblem collections and into other repositories of digitised documents and into library collections in order to create environments where researchers have all the information that they need at their fingertips. You need some tools for making the collections talk to each other.

Chestnova Elena 24:55

CE

Do you think we are there in terms of kind of the level of common conceptualisation of these types of data or do you think the data is simply too diverse and our understanding of them is too... the frameworks are too different to really bring them together right now?

Peter Boot 25:14

PB

Yeah, I think it's wonderful that finally the Distributed Text Services [API] seems to be getting off the ground. This doesn't really help, I think, when you want more specialised information. So, probably, if you would want something like access to dictionaries you would need to have perhaps a more specific protocol in order to be able to actually integrate this into a different environment, at least if you want this to happen in a sort of standardised way. I hope this will come.

One of the things I could also mention is [that] we've been publishing quite a number of collections of letters. Many of the metadata of those letters go into EMLO - Early Modern Letters Online. EMLO is an aggregator of letter metadata. What we haven't yet contributed to, but what we should do is also contribute to the CorrespSearch facility in order to make our letters part of a wider network.

Chestnova Elena 27:09

CE

Yeah, because CorrespSearch has been, I think, really successful in terms of aggregation API services. Do you think its success is precisely because it's specialised?

Peter Boot 27:12

PB

Yes, I think that's an important reason. Letters, of course, are documents with a very clear, but also simple set of metadata which for other genres are not that easy, and also because they're inherently suitable for networking because, well, they're always part of a network and no correspondence network has a clear boundary, so it's very natural that you want to aggregate letter collections, perhaps more so than for other documents.

Chestnova Elena 28:11

CE

Do you think this type of aggregation could also be motivated by the idea of linked data in some ways? So, you may be looking for a text that has some kind of relationship to specific persons, to specific concepts and so on.

Peter Boot 28:29

PB

Linked data is a bit of a buzzword, I think it's been a buzzword for quite long and, at the moment, at least here in the heritage sector in the Netherlands, linked data is also something compulsory. I think it's easier to create a linked data collection than to make it work within the greater linked open data world, let's say. It's easy to associate the URI to a person, but then there are still many institutions creating URIs for persons and then persons are really the most simple thing. Concepts. Yeah, concepts. There are many ways of identifying concepts, so I think that's much easier said than done.

Chestnova Elena 30:01

CE

I think on many points of that, I agree with you. From my own experience of working with linked data, there isn't an easy way of saying, OK, I'm interested in this VIAF and GND. That's actually difficult to do and this is really what you want if you want to start working with this network in some kind of meaningful way.

Peter Boot 30:29

PB

Yes.

Chestnova Elena 30:31

CE

OK, so I think we've covered the territory of the questions that I've proposed and we're very good on time. So, I was wondering if you have thoughts or suggestions for things that I haven't brought up so far.

Peter Boot 30:47

PB

Well, let me check my notes.

Other examples of collections of our Institute that have become part of greater collections. Medieval charters. We've been working on medieval charters long before there were digital connections, and then we went digital and then at some stage or so, people began to think, OK, we need a complete collection of charters from the Netherlands, so that's one of the things that colleagues have worked on. There have been various initiatives that aggregate

various individual resources. My idea is that there are lots of cases where well, reusing by aggregation has not really resulted in something that is actually very usable. And I think one of the reasons is that well, it's usually built with temporary funding and the people who worked on this are very enthusiastic, but move on to other projects. I don't really know what you can do about it. Maybe this sort of initiative should always be housed within a library institution which has perhaps more sense of permanence than the researchers might have. So that's one concern that I noted down.

And... No, I think most of the things that I wrote down, we have also discussed by now.

Chestnova Elena 36:03

CE

Great. Thank you. Actually one question occurred to me when you were talking about large aggregation initiatives and how they really work. Do you think that in comparison to this, the small grassroots initiatives tend to do better and what is the role of this kind of community-based element in the world of sharing, aggregation and so on?

Peter Boot 36:32

PB

Yeah, I think it can be very important. Something like the Distributed Text Services obviously is there because some individual persons thought that this is important. On the other hand, you would never have IIF with just a few individuals. It's also a question of big institutions subscribing to a protocol or an API, or a standard.

Chestnova Elena 37:10

CE

Great. Well, thank you very much. I think we've covered everything.